

An Integrative Approach to Textual History: How Fluid Textual Traditions Challenge Methodology

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Pre-print version. Forthcoming in *Biblische Notizen* 2/2020.

1. Introduction

Scholars studying the Hebrew Bible with a diachronic text-historical approach face perhaps more challenges now than ever before.¹ In essence, it used to be commonplace to take the Masoretic text as a starting point, perform some minor text-critical “corrections” to the text, and then proceed to building complex theories about the redactional layers that eventually resulted in a “final” version. Scholars used to draw a clear line between composition and textual transmission.² In addition to the epistemological critiques of the diachronic approach,³ the sheer quantity of textual material from the Second Temple Period at our disposal after the discovery of the Dead Sea Scrolls seriously challenges traditional methodologies of studying textual history. Coupled with an increasing appreciation of the text-critical value of the “rewritten” Hebrew scriptures,⁴ Septuagint,⁵ Old Latin,⁶ and Samaritan material,⁷ we are forced to come to grips with a more fluid concept of sacred texts in Second Temple Judaism. It has become increasingly clear that the now-canonical forms of the books in the Hebrew Bible represent only a snippet of the textual reality in early Judaism and Christianity.

¹ Many scholars have tackled the methodological challenges discussed in this article. See Debel, *Rewritten*, 65-91, for one excellent discussion and references to relevant literature.

² This bias has been recognized by many scholars. See, for example, Pakkala, *Can*, 3-4. Dozeman, *The Book*, 189-190, writes: “The tendency among redaction critics is all too often to privilege or even limit research to the MT in determining the final form of Joshua or any book for that matter.”

³ The epistemological basis of text-critical scholarship has been challenged by various postmodern approaches, as well as new philology. In this contribution, I will not engage with these epistemological discussions; however, I invite the reader to turn to Hendel, *Mind*, 422-443; Hendel, *Steps*, 127-147, 297-316; Pakkala, *Can*, 5.

⁴ E.g., VanderKam, *Questions*, 96-109, and Zahn, *Talking*, 93-119.

⁵ A clear introduction is provided in Tov, *The Text-Critical*.

⁶ E.g., Treballe Barrera, *Old*, 85-94, and Tekoniemi, *A Game*.

⁷ Tov, *Textual*, 79-93.

In the face of textual fluidity, some have decided to abandon diachronic textual studies – especially the source and redaction critical methods – as untenable.⁸ Others have decided to concentrate on single witnesses and manuscripts. While these approaches yield interesting results within their paradigm, I would argue that abandoning a diachronic approach altogether would be to the detriment of biblical scholarship. Especially when asking historical questions, the nature of biblical sources as edited and multi-layered documents must be taken seriously.⁹ In this contribution, I wish to demonstrate that a fruitful way to proceed would be to take the current situation of diversity seriously and broaden the scope of the diachronic approach. An integrative text-historical approach is needed. I will next briefly outline the rationale and assumptions behind the integrative approach. Then, I will apply the approach by giving an analysis of a particularly complex text: the curse upon the rebuilders of Jericho in Joshua 6 and its multiform attestations in different textual witnesses. To conclude, I will discuss some methodological repercussions for the refinement of text-historical research.

2. The Fluidity of Textual Traditions Warrants an Integrative Approach

There was no single book of Joshua or uniform Joshua tradition in the Second Temple Period.¹⁰ It is more accurate to speak about the transmission of Joshua traditions, manifested in various textual forms, when referring to Second Temple Judaism. When studying the transmission of Joshua traditions, the key pieces of textual evidence for an integrative approach are, at least, the Masoretic text (MT), the Septuagint (LXX), the Dead Sea Scrolls, and other late Second Temple texts about Joshua and the conquest of the promised land (e.g., Josephus and Ben Sira). When using the LXX, in the absence of a critical Göttingen edition, one must deal with multiple ancient manuscripts collated in modern editions.¹¹ The form of the earliest translation of Joshua, the so-

⁸ For instance, John Van Seters has heavily criticized the concept of an “editor” in biblical studies: “I have concluded from this study that there never was in antiquity anything like ‘editions’ of literary works that were the result of an ‘editorial’ process, the work of editors or redactors.” Van Seters, *The Edited*, 398.

⁹ This claim also builds upon the conclusions of Müller / Pakkala / Romeny, *Evidence*, 219: “The examples unequivocally show that it is imperative to be aware of the complicated editorial processes behind the texts of the Hebrew Bible. This is especially important if these texts are used for historical investigation.”

¹⁰ For recent treatments on the plurality of Joshua traditions in the Second Temple Period, see De Troyer, *The Textual*, 330-346, and Mäkipelto, *Uncovering*. Beyond studies of textual history, the different and sometimes conflicting images of Joshua have been recently analyzed by Farber, *Images*.

¹¹ See Mäkipelto, *Uncovering*, 17-39.

called Old Greek -text (OG), is often not obvious. In the Dead Sea Scrolls one is confronted with very fragmentary material witnessing to various forms of “biblical” and “rewritten” Joshua texts.¹² As illuminated by discussions about the peculiar manuscript 4QJosh^a it is not possible to categorize the Qumran Joshua witnesses simply as either “biblical” or “rewritten”.¹³ Such a categorization does not work, since single scrolls contain diverse readings.

The book of Joshua is not an anomaly in this regard, as we have learned from the work of several scholars.¹⁴ This state of the evidence warrants an integrative approach to studying textual history. The aim of such an approach is to describe the diachronic development of a textual tradition. The focus should not be on reconstructing a hypothetical “original” text. Rather, the aim is to explain the state of textual plurality from a diachronic perspective and find the most probable temporal relationships between different readings. There are three guiding assumptions behind such an approach.

1. Recent textual criticism has demonstrated the textual plurality of the Hebrew Bible, even at the end of the Second Temple Period. The full publication of the Dead Sea Scrolls, together with a new appreciation of the text-critical value of the LXX and Samaritan sources, has made it clear that the proto-MT was just one textual witness among many.
2. The line between textual criticism (“lower criticism”) and source/redaction criticism (“higher criticism”) has been blurred. There are several large-scale differences between the textual witnesses of the Hebrew Bible, demonstrating that radical editing took place even in the late Second Temple Period. These editorial processes were also more transformative than was previously thought, since even omissions and replacements took place.¹⁵ Several scholars have argued that analyzing so-called documented evidence of

¹² García Martínez, *Light*, 145-147, and Feldman, *The Rewritten*.

¹³ 4QJosh^a is usually listed among the textual witnesses to the biblical book of Joshua, however, evaluated as preserving a non-aligned textual form. See Lange, 3.2.1 Ancient. While Ulrich, *The Dead*, 60, thinks that the scroll holds the earliest reading in the textual history of the book of Joshua in one of its most unique passages, Feldman, 4Q47, 152-163, has recently argued that the scroll held an abbreviated text, and would be better characterized as rewritten. This discussion illustrates the problems of a dichotomous categorization of texts.

¹⁴ Three examples suffice: Tov, *Textual*, 283-326, lists several cases where differing textual evidence preserves different literary editions for the same text; Müller / Pakkala / Romeny, *Evidence*, introduce several examples of large-scale differences in documented evidence; Mäkipelto / Tekoniemi / Tucker, *Large-Scale*, 1-16, deal with large-scale sequence differences in different manuscripts of the same compositions.

¹⁵ See the study by Pakkala, *God's*.

editing should be the new guiding principle when studying the redaction history of Hebrew scriptures.¹⁶

3. As noted earlier, many scholars have demonstrated that the categorization of texts as “biblical” or “rewritten”, reflecting canonical categories, is anachronistic. Therefore, even though one should appreciate the distinctiveness of different sources and compositions, there is no need to exclude the now non-canonical witnesses from a text-historically oriented analysis. In other words, a clear line between composition and reception cannot be drawn. There is a continuum of ongoing interpretation, which is the research subject of an integrative diachronic approach.

3. The Case of Joshua’s Curse and Its Fluid Fulfillments

The curse uttered by Joshua in Josh 6,26, together with its different fulfillments, is a prime example of a fluid textual tradition that resists traditional categories. When one takes all the evidence into account, this tradition challenges both a unilinear approach to textual history, as well as canonical presuppositions. The complex evidence for the textual transmission of this tradition can be found in the following table. The evidence in the table will be discussed next: first, the unique features of each witness are analyzed and, second, they are compared with each other, resulting in a general model of the transmission of this tradition.

¹⁶ This paradigm can be traced back to Tigay, *Empirical*. It has subsequently been taken up by many scholars. For example, the already mentioned Pakkala / Müller / Romeny, *Evidence*, and Mäkipelto, *Uncovering*.

4Q379, frg. 22ii, lines 8-15 ¹⁷	MT Josh 6,26 ¹⁸	OG Josh 6,26	LXX 1 Kgs 16,34 (om L)	MT 1 Kgs 16,34
<p>... ⁸ אַרְוֹר הָאֵשׁ [רור האש] אשר יב[נ]ה את [העי]ר הזאת בבכורו ייסדנה ⁹ [ובצע]י ר'ו ¹⁰ vacat יציבדתיה</p> <p>והנה [ארו]ר א[חד] ¹⁰ [עומד להיו]ת פח יקוש לעמו ומחתה לכל שכנ[י]ו ועמ[ד] ¹¹ [] ם להיות שניהם כלי חמס ושבו ובנו א[ת] ¹² [העיר ה]זאת ויציבו לה חומה ומגדלים לעשות [לעזו] בישראל ושערוניה באפרים] וביהודה ¹³ [רשע וע]שורעה גדלה בבני יעקב ושפ[כ]י [ד]ם ¹⁴ [ועשו חנופה] בארץ ונאצה גדלה כ*מ[ם] על חל בת ציון ¹⁵ [ובחוק ירושלים]]ooooo</p>	<p>וַיִּשְׁבַּע יְהוֹשֻׁעַ בַּעַת הַהִיא לֵאמֹר אַרְוֹר הָאֵשׁ לְפָנַי יְהוָה אַשְׁרֵי יָקוּם וּבָנָה אֶת-הָעִיר הַזֹּאת אֶת-יְרִיחוֹ בְּבָכָרוֹ יִיָּסְדֶנָּה וּבְצַעֲרֵי יָצִיב דְּלִתֶיהָ</p>	<p>καὶ ὄρκισεν Ἰησοῦς ἐν τῇ ἡμέρᾳ ἐκείνῃ ἐναντίον κυρίου λέγων Ἐπικατάρατος ὁ ἄνθρωπος, ὃς οἰκοδομήσει τὴν πόλιν ἐκείνην· ἐν τῷ πρωτοτόκῳ αὐτοῦ θεμελιώσει αὐτήν καὶ ἐν τῷ ἐλαχίστῳ αὐτοῦ ἐπιστήσει τὰς πύλας αὐτῆς.</p> <p>καὶ οὕτως ἐποίησεν Ὁζαν ὁ ἐκ Βαιθηλ· ἐν τῷ Αβιρων τῷ πρωτοτόκῳ ἐθεμελίωσεν αὐτήν καὶ ἐν τῷ ἐλαχίστῳ διασωθέντι ἐπέστησεν τὰς πύλας αὐτῆς</p>	<p>ἐν ταῖς ἡμέραις αὐτοῦ ὠκοδόμησεν Ἀχιηλ ὁ Βαιθηλίτης τὴν Ἱεριχω· ἐν τῷ Αβιρων τῷ πρωτοτόκῳ αὐτοῦ ἐθεμελίωσεν αὐτήν καὶ τῷ Σεγουβ τῷ νεωτέρῳ αὐτοῦ ἐπέστησεν θύρας αὐτῆς κατὰ τὸ ῥῆμα κυρίου, ὃ ἐλάλησεν ἐν χειρὶ Ἰησοῦ υἱοῦ Ναυη.</p>	<p>בְּיָמָיו בְּנָה חֵאֵל בֵּית הָאֵשׁ אֶת-יְרִיחָהּ בְּאֶבְרָם בְּכָרוֹ יָסְדָהּ ובשגיב (ובשגוב) צַעֲרֵרוֹ הָצִיב דְּלִתֶיהָ כְּדַבַּר יְהוָה אֲשֶׁר דָּבַר בְּיַד יְהוֹשֻׁעַ בֶּן-נֹון</p>

¹⁷ The reconstruction follows Feldman, The Rewritten, 99-101. Line numbers are marked in upper indices.

¹⁸ Some elements are highlighted in the table to aid comparison between traditions: boxed elements are differences between MT and OG Joshua and bolded/underlined elements are similarities between the Joshua and 1 Kings traditions.

4Q379	MT Josh 6,26	OG Josh 6,26	LXX 1 Kgs 16,34 (om L)	MT 1 Kgs 16,34
<p> ⁸ C[ursed be anyo]ne who bu[il]ds this [ci]ty ⁹ With [his] firstborn [he shall found it] and with [his yo]ung[est] he shall set up its gates. And behold, an [accur]sed o[ne] ¹⁰ [is arising to becom]e a fowler’s snare to his people and a terror to all hi[s] neighbours. And he will ari[se] ¹¹ [] to become both of them vessels of violence. And they will again build ¹² [t]his [city]. And they will establish for it a wall and towers in order to make[(it) a stronghold of] in Israel and a horrible thing in Ephraim[and in Judah] ¹³ [wickedness. And they made] a great evil {among the sons of Jacob and (they) will po[ur out blo]od} ¹⁴ [And they have done ungodliness] in the land and great defamation *like wa[ter upon the rampart of the Daughter of Zion] ¹⁵ [and within the boundary of Jerusalem] [</p>	<p> And Joshua swore on that day saying: “Cursed be before YHWH anyone who rises and builds this city Jericho. With his firstborn he shall found it, and with his youngest he shall set up its gates. </p>	<p> And Iesous swore on that day before the Lord saying: “Cursed be the person who shall build this city. With his firstborn he shall found it, and with his youngest, he shall set up its gates. And so did Ozan, the son of Baithel. With his firstborn Abiron he founded it and with his youngest, escaping, he set up its gates. </p>	<p> In his day built Achiel the Bethelite Jericho with his firstborn Abiron he founded it, and with his youngest Segub he set up its gates, according to the word of the Lord spoken by Iesous son of Naue. </p>	<p> In his day built Hiel of Bethel Jericho with his firstborn Abiram he founded it and with his youngest Segub he set up its gates according to the word of YHWH spoken by Joshua son of Nun. </p>

3.1 Joshua 6,26

In MT and OG Joshua, the miraculous conquest of Jericho in Joshua 6 ends with a curse uttered by Joshua. According to this curse, anyone who attempted to rebuild the city of Jericho would do so at the cost of their firstborn and youngest children. The meaning of this repercussion has been debated, but in Joshua it likely refers to the death of the children of the rebuilders as the curse is activated.¹⁹ There are three notable variants between the MT and the OG that attest to minor scribal changes within the transmission of the book of Joshua.

First, the majority of the LXX manuscripts place the phrase *ἐναντίον κυρίου* “before the Lord” at the introduction of the curse, while the phrase (לְפָנַי יְהוָה) appears later in the MT, as a part of the curse itself. The OG reading is not entirely clear; however, the majority text given in the table is the likeliest option.²⁰ The different placements of this phrase between the MT and the OG suggest that it may actually be a later gloss made at some point to the Hebrew text of the curse.²¹ Accordingly, Lea Mazor argues that the OG phrase “cursed be the man” without “before YHWH” reflects the more ancient belief that curses themselves have power. The secondary addition of “before YHWH” modified the curse in accordance with the belief that “the operative power” of curses and blessings come from YHWH.²²

Second, the MT reads the verb “to rise” in the phrase אֲשֶׁר יָקוּם וּבְנֶה “who rises and builds”, while the OG only reads *ὃς οἰκοδομήσει* “who shall build”.²³ The Greek *οἰκοδομέω* is always used

¹⁹ Some have argued that there is a reference to the practice of foundation sacrifice known from other sources. This could be especially true in the context of 1 Kgs 16,34 where Hiel could be seen as continuing the wicked ways of Ahab by following this practice. See De Vries, 1 Kings, 205. This suggestion has been questioned by Montgomery, *A Critical*, 287-288.

²⁰ There are two candidates for the OG: either the phrase was originally in the earlier position as witnessed by the majority, or the phrase was missing from the OG as witnessed by A and some other manuscripts. Nelson, *Joshua*, 87, argues for the latter. However, the missing of the phrase from A could also be explained as a secondary development deriving from the Hexaplaric tradition. The Hexaplaric witnesses (b, x, and Syro-Hexapla) transpose “before the Lord” to a location matching with the MT; thus, also losing the earlier OG position for this phrase. The omission of the phrase may therefore have derived from copying this tradition.

²¹ Holmes, *Joshua*, 37.

²² Mazor, *The Origin*, 4. Interestingly, the earlier version of the curse without “before YHWH” is also found in one Hebrew 14th century Masoretic manuscript (De-Rossi 701 = Parma 2174). See De-Rossi, *Variae*, 79. In this manuscript, the phrase “before YHWH” has been secondarily added as a correction to the margin.

²³ The Hexaplaric text secondarily adds “rises” *ἀναστῆσει* to the text in accordance with the MT.

as a translation equivalent for בָּנָה in Joshua. The Hebrew קוּם “to rise”, on the other hand, is always translated with ἵστημι (with or without a prefix). Therefore, it is likely that the verb “to rise” was missing already from the Hebrew *Vorlage* of the OG. The phrase “to rise and build” is similar to Neh 2,18.20, where the people “rise and build” the walls of Jerusalem. Indeed, a secondary addition of “to rise” in the MT could be an amplification towards this kind of formulaic usage of the phrase. Furthermore, Nelson notes that the MT phrase may be seen as a later hendiadys denoting the meaning “tries to build”.²⁴

Third, the MT specifies that the city in question is אֶת-יְרִיחוֹ “Jericho”, whereas the OG only reads τὴν πόλιν ἐκείνην “this city”. This specification seems superfluous, considering the context of the verse in Joshua after the conquest account of Jericho.²⁵ One could therefore argue that the translator would have left it out. However, it is more likely that the shorter text is earlier and that “Jericho” was at some point added to the Hebrew text as a gloss.²⁶ Its absence from the Qumran scroll 4Q379, which will be discussed below, strengthens the suggestion that the explicit mention of “Jericho” did not belong to the earlier form of this text. In fact, its absence in both OG and 4Q379 could be taken as a hint that the curse may have been at some earlier point applied to another city in another context.

To sum up, in the case of these three minor variants, the OG likely preserves the earlier textual form of the curse. This form goes back to an earlier Hebrew text which has been appended with small additions in the proto-MT editing. 4Q379 is also missing these additions, and was thus likely based on a Hebrew text similar to the source text of the OG.²⁷

In addition to these minor variants, the OG has a long plus at the end of the verse which serves as an immediate fulfillment of the curse. In this way, the verse is not merely a prophecy as in the MT, but history that has already been fulfilled. According to this plus, Ozan of Bethel founded the city at the cost of his children. This plus is constructed in a way that syntactically mirrors verse 26 quite closely (“with his firstborn” ... “and with his youngest”). This fulfillment of the

²⁴ Nelson, Joshua, 87.

²⁵ Holmes, Joshua, 37.

²⁶ Boling / Wright, Joshua, 204.

²⁷ Thus also Feldman, *The Rewritten*, 120.

curse should not be ascribed to the OG translator, but it was likely already found in the Hebrew *Vorlage*. Studies of translation technique have concluded that even though exhibiting some freedom in terms of producing good Greek, the OG Joshua translator would likely not have introduced radical changes to the Hebrew text being translated.²⁸ Moreover, the plus contains Greek expressions that seem to reflect Hebrew: for example, the usage of the Greek ἐν-preposition in ἐν τῷ πρωτοτόκῳ αὐτοῦ and ἐν τῷ ἐλαχίστῳ αὐτοῦ reflects the Hebraistic use of the ב-preposition in the expressions בְּבִכְרֹוֹ and בְּעֵצִירוֹ. Also, the phrase καὶ οὕτως ἐποίησεν is a close rendering of the Hebrew וכן עשה, as seen from several other instances of this expression in Joshua (e.g., 4,8; 9,26; 10,1.39).²⁹

The meaning of the latter part of the plus is somewhat unclear, since it is not clear what the participle διασωθέντι “having survived” refers to. Some interpret that Ozan survived the curse,³⁰ while others believe that it was the youngest child who survived the curse.³¹ Whatever is the meaning of the Greek text, however, in light of the similarities with 1 Kgs 16,34, it is possible that the Hebrew *Vorlage* of the OG simply read the proper name of the youngest son “Segub” שגוב. The translator may have understood this name as a verb. Margolis, for instance, noted that in Prov 29,25 the Hebrew יִשָּׁגב “will be secure” is translated with σωθήσεται “will be saved”.³² Another option was provided by Holmes, who suggested that the name of the younger son somehow derives from the verb ישע “to save”.³³ It is probably not possible to reliably reconstruct how שגוב came to be διασωθέντι but since the dependence between Josh 6,26 and 1 Kgs 16,34 is obvious, it is reasonable to assume that the translator of Josh 6,26 found שגוב in his *Vorlage*.³⁴

²⁸ Mäkipelto, *Uncovering*, 24-29.

²⁹ Mazor, *The Curse*, 8.

³⁰ Dozeman, *Joshua*, 316.

³¹ Mazor, *The Curse*, 7.

³² Margolis, *The Book*, 101.

³³ Holmes, *Joshua*, 37.

³⁴ Mazor, *The Curse*, 13, argued that the OG translator had in his *Vorlage* the name שארה “Sheerah”. Mazor notes that the name Οζαν “Ozan” is used in 1 Chr 7,24 where his son’s name is Sheerah. The meaning of the name שארה is derived from the Hebrew verb שָׁאַר which can also mean “to survive” (cf. OG διασωθέντι). Knowing this meaning, the translator, according to Mazor, “presents a midrash on the name, which suits perfectly the intention of the

Considering these observations, it is most probable that the fulfilment of the curse goes back to a different Hebrew *Vorlage*. Thus, it witnesses to the textual plurality of Joshua traditions in the late Second Temple Period. However, it is another question whether the plus is a secondary addition or originally belonged together with the curse. This diachronic question cannot be answered without first considering the other witnesses.

3.2 1 Kings 16,34

1 Kings 16,29-34 serves as an introduction to the events that allegedly took place during King Ahab's reign over Israel. These narratives span over six chapters, and end with the report of King Ahab's death in 1 Kings 22 and the consequent concluding remarks in 1 Kgs 22,39-40. In the beginning of this wider narrative in 1 Kgs 16,29-34, Ahab is introduced as the most wicked king Israel has ever seen. The last verse mentions that during the time of Ahab, a man named Hiel from Bethel rebuilt Jericho. In accordance with Josh 6,26, this rebuilding was done at the cost of his firstborn and his youngest son. As highlighted in the table, this verse is closely related to Josh 6,26 and shares most expressions.

The verse, however, also differs from Josh 6,26. First, the framing is different, reflecting the editorial techniques with which the fulfilment was added to the context of Kings. The fulfilment is linked with the days of Ahab by using the introductory formula *בְּיָמָיו* "in his days".

Furthermore, the fulfilment is followed by a reference to Joshua: "according to the word of YHWH spoken by Joshua son of Nun."

Second, there are some apparent differences in the text of the fulfilment itself. The name Abiron as the firstborn is shared in both traditions, but the person doing the building is different: Joshua has *Oζαν*, while MT has *Αχιηλ*. Rare proper names tend to get corrupted in the textual

verse." There are problems with this suggestion. First, the decision to translate the second name in the verse in a midrashic way seems improbable when one considers the overall style of the Joshua translator. Second, a reference to 1 Chr 7,24 seems far-fetched since there is a closer parallel in 1 Kgs 16,34. Moreover, 1 Chr 7,24 is a problematic text: for example, in the MT it is dealing with the geographical location *אֶזְנֵן שְׂאֲרָה* "Uzzen-Sheerah" and not a person named Ozan and his son Sheerah. Mazor gives her own solution to this textual problem (Mazor, *The Curse*, 14-20), but the solution is based on many uncertain assumptions.

transmission of manuscripts. It is not clear what the original name in either of the traditions was: for instance, the Old Latin text, which quite often preserves the OG, reads in Josh 6,26 *Azael* instead of Ozan. This reading would already be closer to *Αχιηλ* in 1 Kgs 16,34.³⁵ Therefore, it is not clear whether there is an actual difference between the names or whether this is merely a result of textual corruption.

It is important to also highlight what Mazor demonstrated: the Greek translations of Josh 6,26 and 1 Kgs 16,34 differ in many details.³⁶ First, while Joshua refers to the person as *ὁ ἐκ Βαιθηλ* “from Bethel”, Kings uses the form *ὁ Βαιθηλίτης* “Bethelite”. Second, in Kings the possessive suffixes of “his firstborn” and “his youngest” are translated, while Joshua leaves them untranslated. Third, Kings uses the word *νέος* for the youngest while Joshua reads *ἐλάχιστος*. Fourth, Kings uses the word *θύρα* for “gate” while Joshua reads *πύλη*. These differences in the translations suggest that the verses are not dependent on each other on the Greek level. Both are independent translations from a Hebrew *Vorlage*.

These observations point to the conclusion that the Hebrew source text of the fulfilment is very similar in both OG Josh 6,26 and 1 Kgs 16,34. The differences on the Greek level are due to corruption in textual transmission and differences in translational choices. The main difference in the Hebrew text of these traditions was in the different framings of the verse in their respective contexts.

Finally, the largest text-critical issue pertaining to 1 Kgs 16,34 should still be discussed. While 1 Kgs 16,34 is present in the majority of the LXX manuscripts, the verse is completely missing from the Lucianic witnesses. The Lucianic text often preserves OG readings, in comparison with other manuscripts that may have gone through a revision towards the proto-MT text. This is especially evident in the *kaige* sections of Samuel-Kings.³⁷ In this instance, we are situated outside the *kaige* section; nevertheless, there are no good reasons to assume that the verse would

³⁵ Margolis, *The Book*, 101, offered one possible solution for how *Οζαν* may have resulted from textual corruption of the Hebrew “Hiel”.

³⁶ Mazor, *The Curse*, 7-9.

³⁷ See, for example, Fernández Marcos, *Scribes*, 27-37.

have been dropped out in the transmission of the Lucianic text.³⁸ First, there are no features in the text that would normally cause a scribal mistake. Second, based on our knowledge of the Lucianic revision, the reviser would likely not have intentionally omitted such a verse.³⁹ There are no theologically or ideologically problematic ideas in this verse that would have caused its deliberate omission. Furthermore, it seems that Josephus was using a text from which this verse was missing (*Antiquitates Judaicae* 8.316-318).⁴⁰ Therefore, it is more likely that the Lucianic manuscripts and Josephus were based on an earlier version of the text that did not yet contain this verse.

Indeed, this conclusion is strengthened by the observation that the verse has several signs of being a later addition. The beginning בְּיָמָיו “in his days” can be interpreted as the literary device with which the scribal addition was made and inserted into the preceding narrative. That this literary device was used specifically for this context is revealed by the fact that in the parallel addition in OG Josh 6,26 the phrase is missing. Also, the content of the verse is not as such connected to the preceding or following textual material, which makes it a loose verse in this context.

In sum, it is likely that 1 Kgs 16,34 was missing from the OG, because the verse was already missing from its Hebrew *Vorlage*. Hence, the Lucianic version of Kings represents here the earliest layer of the evolution of this passage. It preserves a state of the text before this fulfilment was inserted to Kings. The verse was added at the end of 1 Kgs 16 in the proto-MT editing, and was consequently also added to the LXX as part of the early Hebraizing revision that affected all the other manuscripts but the Lucianic.⁴¹

³⁸ Hebraizing corrections can also exist outside the *kaige* sections and in these cases the Lucianic text may sometimes represent OG. See, for example, Aejmelaeus, *Kaige*, 169-184.

³⁹ On the typical features of the Lucianic reviser see Fernández Marcos, *The Septuagint*, 230.

⁴⁰ The verse is also missing from the quotation by Lucifer of Cagliari in *De non conveniendo cum haereticis* chapter 3. It may be that Lucifer did not have the verse in his base text; however, since this is a non-continuous quotation, it cannot be used as evidence for the absence of the verse from Lucifer's base text. For Lucifer's text about Ahab and discussion see Kauhanen, Lucifer, 112-122, 389-390.

⁴¹ Unfortunately, there are no translational features that would decisively set the translation of v. 34 apart from the OG translation. The renderings are either commonplace (e.g., οἰκοδομέω “to build” or ῥῆμα “word”) or the Hebrew lexemes are rare in Samuel-Kings (e.g., יסד “to lay foundation” or צעיר “youngest”). The one feature that hints towards *kaige* is the translation of the Hebrew יָבֵן with ἐν χεῖρῃ in a context where it obviously does not mean

3.3 4Q379

At this point, the last source should be included to the discussion. The Hebrew scroll 4Q379 is part of the so-called rewritten Joshua scrolls, or the “Apocryphon of Joshua”.⁴² This very fragmentarily preserved scroll preserves passages dealing with the crossing of the Jordan and the conquest of Jericho and Ai. In addition to some narrative, it infuses the story with speeches, prayers, and praises.⁴³ While there has been some debate on the issue, 4Q379 is likely not a sectarian text produced by the Qumran community.⁴⁴

The table presents lines 8-15 from fragment 22, column ii. Preceding this text, on lines 1-7, words of praise uttered by Joshua are preserved. Line 7 reads: “When Josh[u]a fin[ish]ed pr[aising and giving] than[ks] with [his] songs of praise [he said:]”, and the curse follows. It would be hard to reconstruct the text of the curse if another scroll, 4Q175 (*The Testimonia*), had not preserved a quotation of this text. 4Q175 is a collection of five quotations, out of which the last is a clear quotation of 4Q379.⁴⁵

According to Stegemann’s arrangement of the fragments of 4Q379, the curse comes after the crossing of Jordan and before the conquest of Ai. It is thus usually assumed that the curse is related to the city of Jericho. However, this is not certain, since there are no explicit mentions of Jericho in the curse itself. The scroll only reads “this city”, as was the case with OG Josh 6,26. The text might, in fact, also refer to another city: in 4Q175 which quotes this text, “Jerusalem” is

literally “by hand”. A similar usage is found in 1 Kgs 16,12 where the Lord speaks בְּיַד יְהוֹנָן הַנְּבִיא “by the prophet Jehu.” The OG translates this more dynamically, so that the Lord speaks “to the prophet Jehu” πρὸς Ἰου τὸν προφήτην. However, since the OG also uses ἐν χειρὶ to translate יָד elsewhere with a similar meaning (e.g., 1 Kgs 8:53.56), this is not conclusive evidence. This translation-technical observation does nevertheless strengthen the conclusion that the verse may come from *kaige*. I wish to thank Tuukka Kauhanen for pointing out these translational details to me at the EABS Annual Conference in Warsaw 2019.

⁴² These include 4Q378, 4Q379, 4Q522, 4Q123, 5Q9, and Mas¹⁰³⁹⁻²¹¹. The name “Apocryphon of Joshua” has been used in research because of the assumption that these six scrolls are copies of the same work. This has been argued most elaborately by Tov, *The Rewritten*, 233-256. However, Feldman, *The Rewritten*, 187-193, has demonstrated that there is not enough evidence to assume a single composition.

⁴³ Feldman, *The Rewritten*, 74-127.

⁴⁴ See Dimant, *Between*, 105-134; Tov, *The Rewritten*, 254-255; Berthelot, *In Search*, 347.

⁴⁵ On questions related to the reconstruction see Newsom, 378-379, 237-288, and Feldman, *The Rewritten*, 101-104. A concise introduction to 4Q175, its contents, and research can be found in Brooke, *Testimonia*, 391-392.

mentioned explicitly. Moreover, in fifty-five of the instances of the phrase אֶת-הָעִיר הַזֹּאת “this city” in the Hebrew Bible, fifty-three refer explicitly to Jerusalem.⁴⁶ Thus, while Jericho is a likely candidate, one cannot be sure which city is rebuilt in 4Q379.

In any case, 4Q379 contains another fulfilment of Joshua’s curse. Unlike the one in Joshua and 1 Kings, this interpretation does not explicitly mention any names. It states that a wicked person will rise. Then there is a gap in the text, after which two persons are mentioned who will do the rebuilding. This deed is condemned harshly, and it is said that it brings great defamation to the land. Some have argued that this is a reference to the Hasmonean leader John Hyrcanus and his sons who, according to archaeological evidence, were involved in a major building project at Jericho.⁴⁷ Whether this is the case or not, the existence of this text alongside the version in Joshua and Kings is a testament to the fact that the curse of Joshua was interpreted in different ways by different scribal communities.

3.4 General Developmental Trajectories

What does the textual development of Joshua’s curse look like, in light of all the evidence discussed? The best theory of diachronic textual development is the one that best explains all the evidence. I would argue that the evidence can be best explained by assuming a single short core text, which was the earliest version of the curse: “Cursed be anyone who builds this city. With his firstborn he shall found it, and with his youngest he shall set up its gates.”⁴⁸ In different textual traditions and scribal communities, this curse was interpreted in different ways: like a branching tree, it developed in different directions.

Considering first the narrative of the conquest of Jericho, it is likely that this short curse was not originally part of the narrative at all.⁴⁹ The curse has been secondarily added to the end of the narrative with the help of the introductory formula בְּעַת הַהֵיא “on that day”, which is a common

⁴⁶ Berthelot, *In Search*, 348.

⁴⁷ I have discussed the possible socio-historical context of this text in Mäkipelto, *Rewriting*.

⁴⁸ In this context I will refrain from postulating an original *Sitz im Leben* for such a curse. For some suggestions see Fritz, *Das Buch*, 74.

⁴⁹ Thus also Mazor, *The Curse*, 22.

phrase in Deuteronomy for making secondary supplementations.⁵⁰ The addition of the curse was only the tip of the iceberg, since the story about the conquest of Jericho in Joshua 6 had likely undergone several stages of editing already before the addition. This is evident already from the documented evidence: when comparing the OG with the MT, one notices several additions in the MT that were not yet present in the Hebrew *Vorlage* of the OG.⁵¹ In particular, many priestly elements have been secondarily strengthened in the narrative.⁵² Beyond the textual evidence, due to the many problems in the progress of the narrative, source critics usually distinguish two or more layers in the composition of the Jericho account.⁵³

From a redaction-critical point of view, the curse against the rebuilders of Jericho is likely a late addition in both Joshua and 1 Kings. Considering Josh 6,26, Noth already regarded it as an addition by the Deuteronomistic editor which was made together with 1 Kgs 16,34.⁵⁴ After Noth, many others have attributed this verse to some late Deuteronomistic editor.⁵⁵ Even though the curse has no parallels in the Hebrew Bible, it can be seen as an application of Deut 13,16 which cautions against rebuilding cities that have been devoted to YHWH.⁵⁶ There are also similarities with Deut 28,52 where the destruction of city walls by the enemy is attributed to a curse caused by disobedience to YHWH.⁵⁷ Therefore, the addition of such a curse to Joshua 6 was likely inspired by Deuteronomy. Also, in 1 Kings the mention of the curse is usually taken as a later addition, attributed to some Deuteronomistic redaction. Already von Rad attributed both verses to a series of Deuteronomistic redactions which sought to demonstrate the fulfilment of ancient prophecies in the history of Israel.⁵⁸ These redaction-critical conclusions are confirmed by the

⁵⁰ Loewenstamm, *The Formula*, 99-104.

⁵¹ Nelson, *Joshua*, 83-85, gives a helpful table of the two versions and argues that OG preserves the “unrevised text”, while the MT introduces several revisions. See also De Troyer, *The Ultimate*, 31-32.

⁵² Dozeman, *Joshua*, 324-325.

⁵³ De Troyer, *The Ultimate*, 26-31, gives a brief summary of these models. See also Dozeman, *Joshua*, 320-325.

⁵⁴ Noth, *The Deuteronomistic*, 65.

⁵⁵ E.g., Fritz, *Das Buch*, 74, and Bieberstein, *Josua*, 294-296.

⁵⁶ Römer, *The So-Called*, 135.

⁵⁷ Dozeman, *Joshua*, 336.

⁵⁸ Von Rad, *Studies*, 74-91.

text-critical evidence, since the fulfilment of the curse is missing from MT Joshua and the whole curse was absent from OG 1 Kings 16.⁵⁹

Moving beyond redaction criticism, however, the text-critical problem remains whether the fulfilment of the curse was added first to Joshua or Kings, and which one of the two texts refers to the other. This cannot be solved conclusively. Since in 1 Kings the curse is already connected to Jericho, it is perhaps more likely that the curse and the fulfilment was taken from the context of Joshua 6, where the Jericho narrative is first narrated.⁶⁰ Joshua offers a far more suitable original context for the genesis of such a fulfilment. The verse in 1 Kings is also much fuller, with more extensive editorial framing, which suggests its nature as a later adaptation of the fulfilment to the context of Kings. The explicit reference to Joshua further strengthens this theory.

However, while the addition in Kings may come from the Hebrew *Vorlage* of OG Joshua, the fulfilment of the curse is likely also a secondary addition in Joshua, made to the Hebrew *Vorlage* before the OG translation. This is suggested both by the redaction-critical observations made above and by the text-critical consideration that it would be hard to conceive why the passage would have been intentionally omitted from the MT. It could certainly be argued that it was lost due to *homoioteleuton* caused by the similar ending at the end of verse 26 (“he shall set up its gates” ... “he shall set up its gates”). However, it would have been curious that a scribal lapse happened to delete a coherent section, especially in the case of verse Josh 6:26, which is divergent in the wider context and would have thus likely enhanced the vigilance of the scribe. Therefore, the opposite solution is more likely. In other words, the repetition at the end of the verse may be taken as evidence of the editorial technique of resumptive repetition (*Wiederaufnahme*), which was used by the scribe(s) who added the legend to the Hebrew *Vorlage* of OG.

Finally, that the curse about the rebuilder of Jericho was interpreted and expanded already in the “biblical” text should affect the way we evaluate the passage in 4Q379. The interpretation in 4Q379 is not a “parabiblical” addition; the text simply follows the scribal tradition of interpreting

⁵⁹ Thus also Rösel, *Tradition*, 184: “there are good reasons to conclude that *both* texts in question are secondary supplements with the aim of emphasizing the Deuteronomistic scheme of prophetic foretelling and historical fulfilment.”

⁶⁰ Thus also Mazor, *The Curse*, 23.

the curse for its audience. Moreover, we have no way of knowing which one of these fulfilments came first. The fulfilment in 4Q379 has been understood as a reference to a Hasmonean leader, but the editorial changes attested between MT and OG Joshua have also been dated by some to the Hasmonean times.⁶¹ What we have is simply a case of a Hebrew text being edited in different directions by different scribes. Both interpretations achieved at least some authority, since OG Joshua was used by the Alexandrian community and 4Q379 was further quoted in the Messianic text of 4Q175. Furthermore, since it is impossible to evaluate the temporal relationship of these fulfilments, one is reminded that unilinear models of diachronic textual growth are too simplistic. In this case, the text has developed more like the branches of a tree, as this tradition was transmitted by different scribal communities.

4. Methodological Repercussions for Diachronic Methodology

Fluid textual traditions challenge diachronic methodology in many ways. The case of the different fulfilments of Joshua's curse is not unique in its fluidity.⁶² Therefore, at least three methodological repercussions should be underlined for the refinement of methodology more broadly.

First, when studying the transmission of textual traditions from a diachronic perspective, there are no clear boundaries between textual criticism and source/redaction criticism. The text-critical evidence of the curse on the rebuilder of Jericho attests to considerable intentional editing, which serves as a continuity for the editorial developments suggested by redaction criticism. The preservation of our textual evidence is random, which is why some of the editorial developments can be discerned by comparing manuscripts and some by building theories based on features in single texts.

Second, all the evidence must be included in the analysis, including texts that are now considered non-canonical. Texts appear fixed only if one precludes evidence from the outset. 4Q379 has not been accepted to any modern canons, but it is clearly a witness to the textual growth of Josh

⁶¹ De Troyer, *Rewriting*, 57.

⁶² Another fluid case is the transmission of the Pentateuchal traditions. When one takes into account the text- and redaction-critical theories of the Pentateuch, as well as the "rewritten" traditions, no simple models of textual transmission suffice. See, for example, the studies in footnote 4.

6,26. Moreover, the text was authoritative for the author of 4Q175. We should not assume that the editorial techniques attested in such texts are essentially different from the scribal processes that affected the Hebrew Bible. When one integrates all of the evidence to the study of Joshua traditions in the Second Temple Period, a picture of considerable flexibility and scribal creativity arises. This fluidity illuminates the worlds of different scribal communities, not only the ones that embraced the MT.

Third, the textual and editorial history of the Hebrew Bible is often imagined as a relatively unilinear development. This is perhaps because the MT is seen as an endpoint of textual development, as the “final text”. Even source and redaction critics often begin with the MT and start reconstructing a linear history of its development. The textual evidence witnessing to the development of Joshua’s curse cannot be explained in this way. The fulfilment of the curse was edited by scribes in three different directions (that we know of): one can be seen in Joshua, the second in 1 Kings, and the third in 4Q379. The fulfilments in Joshua and Kings are clearly connected and are likely products of the deuteronomically inspired scribal circles, but the fulfilment in 4Q379 likely comes from a different community.⁶³ Thus, an integrative approach to text-historical studies highlights the plurality of voices in the Second Temple Period.

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⁶³ I have suggested in Mäkipelto, *Rewriting*, that this fulfilment derives ultimately from Samaritan scribal circles.

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Abstract

Some texts in the Hebrew Bible exist in particularly fluid forms. This becomes clear when one compares all of the extant documented evidence, beyond the anachronistic categories of

“biblical” and “non-biblical”. Nevertheless, the repercussions of this textual fluidity for text-historical methodology has not yet been investigated enough. This contribution examines the transmission and interpretation of the curse upon the builder of Jericho as preserved in various divergent traditions of Joshua, 1 Kings, and Qumran scrolls. Methodological repercussions of this case for the diachronic study of the Hebrew Bible are discussed. It is argued that an integrative approach combining a plurality of texts and methods is needed.

Deutschsprachige Kurzfassung

Dass einige Texte des Alten Testaments eine besonders instabile Form haben, wird deutlich, wenn man alle erhaltenen Textzeugnisse miteinander vergleicht. Die Tatsache, dass viele Manuskripte im Einzelfall voneinander abweichen, ist in Bezug auf die texthistorische Methodik noch nicht ausreichend bewertet worden. Dieser Beitrag untersucht die Entwicklung und Auslegung des Fluches über den Wiederaufbau von Jericho in Josua und 1. Könige sowie in den Texten aus Qumran. Methodische Auswirkungen dieses Falles auf das diachrone Studium der hebräischen Bibel werden diskutiert. Es zeigt sich, dass ein Ansatz, der eine Vielzahl von Texten und Methoden kombiniert, erforderlich ist.